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D5.2 Enhanced and Curated Training Resources Aligned with Software Best Practices: Initial release

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Abstract

This deliverable outlines the methodology followed for collecting and curating training resources and best practices related to research software quality and link them in the RSQKit and the EVERSE training registry.

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Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the methodology followed in WP5 to collect and curate a list of training resources on research software and align it with the good practices published in the Research Software Quality Kit (RSQKit). Our work extensively builds on the work done in WP2 (best practices, RSQKit) and WP4 (collection of all digital research skills training resources within the science clusters in the EVERSE project).

The proposed methodology includes a curation workflow which filters and categorises training materials, enriches each of them with metadata (i.e., name, description, URL, quality dimension) and describes them with a set of keywords (tags) from a vocabulary of keywords defined and shared across different activities in EVERSE (including TechRadar, EVERSE training registry and RSQKit). Training materials are then ingested in the EVERSE training registry, a platform for storing training material metadata, and linked from the RSQKit task pages through inline annotations.

Finally, the initial architecture and results of the overall system are presented. Future releases will increase the coverage and wealth of training resources aligned with task pages in the RSQKit.

1 Introduction

The WP5 in EVERSE aims to align, adapt, extend, and curate research software quality training resources across research communities, building around the Research Software Quality Kit (RSQKit), and to deliver a recognition framework for rewarding scientists and trainers for their contributions to research software, adapting existing platforms aligned to larger research attribution initiatives. In this deliverable (D5.2), we build on previous work on 1) the collection and landscaping of best practices for research software among the EVERSE project, 2) the collection of training materials among EVERSE pilots and science communities; and 3) the development of the RSQKit as a knowledge hub of best practices for research software to align best practices against existing training materials. Our demonstrator leverages the RSQKit as a central knowledge hub and the EVERSE training registry (based on life Sciences Training e-Support Service ([TeSS](#)) built by the Elixir project) for hosting training materials, establishing a maintainable workflow for linking and propagating curated training materials in both platforms. Thanks to this work, training material curators and RSQKit editors can work in parallel, using a simple tagging mechanism to refer to training materials in EVERSE TeSS.

The resources used in this deliverable are available online:

- [EVERSE TeSS instance](#)
- [RSQKit](#)
- [GitHub](#) repository of curated training materials [1]

The remainder of the deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 2 describes in detail the related work leveraged in this deliverable from other EVERSE work packages, as well as the method followed to curate the training materials and link them to existing best practices in the RSQKit.
- Section 3 describes the demonstrator and its status, showing the workflow for ingesting and annotating training materials in EVERSE TeSS, and how to link them from existing or new RSQKit pages.
- Section 4 describes the maintainability and sustainability aspects of the proposed solution as well as future points of improvement.

2 Methods

In order to enhance, curate and align existing training materials to best practices, we build on the previous outcomes from WP4 (EOSC Science Cluster Pilots and Driver projects) and WP2 (Community-led best practices for developing high-quality research software). This section outlines the previous efforts we use as a foundation in subsection 2.1, followed by the curation process to enrich each of the training materials collaboratively (subsection 2.2), and how a link was established between training materials and existing good practices.

2.1 Previous work

We build on three key EVERSE results: the quality landscaping survey performed [2], [3] as part of WP2 to determine the adoption of best practices among the EVERSE partners; a collection of training materials across research communities from WP4 [4] and the organisation of the RSQKit Knowledge Hub [5], which collects best practices and their organization according to quality dimensions. We summarise each of these results below.

2.1.1 EVERSE Software quality landscaping survey (MS4)

The second milestone in WP2 [2] aimed at providing “a comprehensive landscaping of the best practices on software quality within the research communities contributing to the EVERSE project. This objective was met by preparing and conducting a survey with the partners, in which the established practices were explored” [3].

The survey included quality aspects regarding common practices for improving software performance, standardization, usability, testing, reliability, security, and documentation. Each aspect of the survey was assessed in terms of importance to the respondents and their impression of the stage of implementation within their research infrastructures. Nearly twenty participants answered the survey, providing a first prioritisation for the best practices and tasks to be included in the RSQKit.

2.1.2 Mapping of the stocktake of training materials across the training initiatives in the research communities (MS15)

As part of WP4, each science cluster in EVERSE was tasked with providing the training resources relevant to their research software ecosystem. As a result, a list of training materials was grouped into common topics, which were further assessed with an online survey [4]. The final training list is organised around 31 different categories, which range from good practices (e.g., versioning, reproducibility, software citation, etc.) to research data management, cloud computing or parallel programming.

The list of training materials was the starting point used as reference for this deliverable.

2.1.3 Knowledge Hub Delivery and Best Practices for Research Software Development (D2.2)

The EVERSE Research Software Quality Kit (RSQKit) [5] (developed as part of WP2 using the results of MS4 [2], [3]) describes a set of task pages with common tasks for following good practices in research software engineering [6]. These tasks range from practices for

establishing continuous integration pipelines in a source code repository to practices for test automation, code quality or metadata and publishing. Task pages are organized according to eleven quality dimensions, agreed at the second General Assembly Meeting and inspired by existing quality frameworks such as [ISO/IEC 25010](#) and principles such as FAIR4RS [7]. We summarize them below:

- **Compatibility:** degree to which a product, system or component can exchange information with other products, systems or components, and/or perform its required functions while sharing the same common environment and resources.
- **FAIRness:** degree to which research software adheres to the FAIR principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. These principles, adapted for research software, aim to enhance the discoverability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of software, thereby maximizing its value and impact in scientific research
- **Flexibility:** degree to which a product can be adapted to changes in its requirements, contexts of use or system environment.
- **Functional suitability:** characteristic that represents the degree to which a product or system provides functions that meet stated and implied needs when used under specified conditions.
- **Interaction Capability:** degree to which a product or system can be interacted with by specified users to exchange information via the user interface to complete specific tasks in a variety of contexts of use.
- **Maintainability:** degree of effectiveness and efficiency with which a product or system can be modified to improve it, correct it or adapt it to changes in environment, and in requirements.
- **Performance Efficiency:** degree to which a product performs its functions within specified time and throughput parameters and is efficient in the use of resources (such as CPU, memory, storage, network devices, energy, materials...) under specified conditions.
- **Reliability:** degree to which a system, product or component performs specified functions under specified conditions for a specified period of time.
- **Safety:** degree to which a product under defined conditions avoids a state in which human life, health, property, or the environment is endangered.
- **Security:** degree to which a product or system defends against attack patterns by malicious actors and protects information and data so that persons or other products or systems have the degree of data access appropriate to their types and levels of authorization.
- **Sustainability:** capacity of the software to endure. In other words, sustainability means that the software will continue to be available in the future, on new platforms, meeting new needs.

In this deliverable, we use the task pages to link to different curated training materials. The quality dimensions are used to tag each training material with the corresponding quality dimension they help to improve.

2.2 Training resource curation and RSQKit alignment

Starting from the list of resources gathered in MS15 [4], a curation process was established in WP5 to refine, expand and enhance the training material list. This collaborative effort, initially maintained in a shared spreadsheet was later moved to [GitHub](#) and published with a release [1] to ease tracking issues and opening contributions to all project participants.

The curation process was done in three consecutive steps. First, all training resources were categorised according to their type, and duplicates were removed. Five main categories were identified:

1. **Training repositories and registries:** Repositories and registries containing training materials such as courses and guides (e.g., Elixir TeSS, [ENVRI Hub](#), [SSHOC Marketplace](#)). These registries contain the material we aim to link from RSQKit task pages.
2. **Training material and curricula:** Individual courses, guidelines or recommendations for improving specific research software engineering skills or best practices.
3. **Training schools and events:** Events aimed at training researchers and students from the different EVERSE clusters. These events are usually course descriptions, with no link to the taught training materials.
4. **Reports and publications:** Scientific articles, project reports which outline general recommendations (e.g., the FAIR principles publication [8]) but do not necessarily include training materials
5. **Projects:** Community initiatives for collecting examples (e.g., Awesome lists) discussing standards (e.g., [CodeMeta](#)) or services for browsing examples of tools following best practices and recommendations.

From these categories, “**Training material and curricula**” is the one mostly used to link existing RSQKit task pages to training materials, as these training materials complement and provide additional examples to the contents already in the RSQKit.

As a second step, each training material was annotated with its corresponding title, original URL, a short description about its contents or purpose, the scientific cluster or domain it belonged to, the software quality dimension it addressed (based on the list described in [Section 2.1.3](#)), and a set of keywords to ease its findability.

Finally, in a third step, each task page in RSQKit was aligned using the same keywords of its corresponding training materials. Table 1 shows an overview of the different task pages tagged in RSQKit, along with their URL and keywords used.

Task page (URL)	Keywords used
Continuous integration / continuous development (https://everse.software/RSQKit/ci_cd)	"ci" "cd" "ci/cd" "continuous integration" "continuous deployment"
Citing software (https://everse.software/RSQKit/citing_software)	"citation" "cff"
Code review (https://everse.software/RSQKit/code_review)	"code review"
Creating a good README (https://everse.software/RSQKit/creating_good_readme)	"readme"
Documenting software (https://everse.software/RSQKit/documenting_software)	"documentation" "readme" "sphinx" "readthedocs"
Improving environmental sustainability (https://everse.software/RSQKit/improving_environmental_sustainability)	"sustainability" "environment"
Selecting a programming Language (https://everse.software/RSQKit/languages_tools_infrastructures)	"r" "python" "c" "programming language" "julia" "java"
Licensing software (https://everse.software/RSQKit/licensing_software)	"license"

Organising software projects (https://everse.software/RSQKit/organising_software_projects)	"organise project"
Packaging software (https://everse.software/RSQKit/packaging_releasing_software)	"package" "release" "pypi" "github"
Releasing software (https://everse.software/RSQKit/releasing_software)	"release" "github" "gitlab"
Creating reproducible environments (https://everse.software/RSQKit/reproducible_software_environments)	"reproducible" "environment" "docker" "singularity" "singularity" "reproducible environment" "virtual environment"
Creating good code documentation (https://everse.software/RSQKit/documenting_software)	"documentation" "code comments" "readme" "mkdocs" "readthedocs"
Creating software identifiers (https://everse.software/RSQKit/software_identifiers)	"identifier" "release" "versioning"
Software metadata (https://everse.software/RSQKit/software_metadata)	"metadata" "codemeta" "cff"
Task automation through GitHub actions (https://everse.software/RSQKit/task_automation_github_actions)	"ci/cd" "task automation" "github" "action"
Task automation through GitLab actions (https://everse.software/RSQKit/task_automation_gitlab_ci_cd)	"ci/cd" "task automation" "gitlab"
Testing software (https://everse.software/RSQKit/testing_software)	"testing"
Using version control (https://everse.software/RSQKit/using_version_control)	"version control" "git" "github" "gitlab"
Writing readable code (https://everse.software/RSQKit/writing_readable_code)	"readable code" "robust code" "reusable code"

Table 1: Task pages in RSQKit (best practices) and their corresponding keywords for finding related materials in EVERSE TeSS

3 Results

The EVERSE [training registry](#) is a service containing training materials and events designed to store and ease the findability of existing training materials associated with research software engineering good practices. Figure 1 shows an overview of the main architecture and workflow to:

1. **Ingest (new) training materials:** A training material contributor edits a collaborative spreadsheet in the shared curated materials [source code repository](#) which is then automatically harvested by the EVERSE training materials registry (along with its corresponding metadata).
2. **Link RSQKit pages to existing training materials:** First, a RSQKit contributor annotates an RSQKit page with keywords as shown in **Code snippet 1**. These keywords are then used to issue a search query in the EVERSE training registry, accessible by a button on the RSQKit page.

Figure 1. Architecture for curating and propagating training materials in EVERSE.

Figure 2 shows an example of how the training materials are displayed in a task page in RSQKit. After tagging the target page with keywords as displayed in **Code snippet 1** (see the "url" used, which contains the target keywords), the annotated page will display a new section named "Training" (**Figure 2**, top) with a link. When followed, the page will open the training materials registry with the same keywords as used in the page annotation (**Figure 2**, bottom).

```

---
title: Continuous Integration and Continuous Delivery/Deployment
description: How can you use CI/CD in software development?
contributors: ["Aleksandra Nenadic"]
page_id: ci_cd
indicators: [software_has_ci-tests]
related_pages:
  your_tasks: [task_automation_github_actions, task_automation_gitlab_ci_cd]
training:
  - name: EVERSE TeSS url: https://everse-training.app.cern.ch
    registry: TeSS
    url: https://everse-
training.app.cern.ch/materials?q=%22ci%22+%22cd%22+%22ci%2Fcd%22+%22continuous+integration%22+
%22continuous+deployment%22
---

```

Code snippet 1. Annotations of the RSQKit page on continuous integration and deployment to link training resources using the common keywords shown in Table 1.

The figure illustrates the connection between a task page in RSQKit and its corresponding training materials in EVERSE TeSS. The top part shows the 'More information' section of the RSQKit page, which includes the title 'Continuous Integration and Continuous Delivery/Deployment', a description, contributors, and a training link to 'https://everse-training.app.cern.ch'. A blue arrow points from this training link to the 'Training materials' section in EVERSE TeSS. In the TeSS section, a search query is shown: '"ci" "cd" "ci/cd" "continuous integration" "continuous deployment"', which matches the keywords used in the RSQKit page. The search results show a material titled 'HSF - Continuous Integration / Continuous Development (CI/CD)' with tags for 'ci cd', 'continuous integration', and 'continuous deployment'.

Figure 2. An example displaying a task page in RSQKit and its corresponding training materials in EVERSE TeSS through a search query. The keywords that enable the search are the same ones used to annotate training materials.

4 Conclusions and Future Work

This deliverable describes how the first collection of training materials has been curated and aligned to the RSQKit best practices task pages through the EVERSE TeSS Training registry. A flexible workflow has been designed to:

- Allow training material curators including new training materials into the training registry through a shared GitHub repository
- Enable RSQKit curators to link to existing training materials through common keywords directly from RSQKit pages. Relevant training materials are then shown in the RSQKit, establishing a link between both platforms.

At the time of writing this deliverable, the first list of curated training materials [1] is being ingested in the EVERSE TeSS training registry, and all RSQKit task pages have been annotated with the same keywords used to curate the corresponding training materials. New updates are expected to occur regularly until the end of the project.

As for future work, owing to the training material curation process we have detected knowledge gaps in RSQKit (e.g., task pages for good practices like improving software performance, logging, etc), which have been reported and will be addressed in future releases.

5 References

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